

ENGLISH LEARNING APPS: THE AI REVOLUTION

Student: Xadicha Shukhratova,

Bachelor's degree, English Education faculty,

Kimyo International University in Tashkent (KIUT)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15728780>

Annotation: This article explores the impact of artificial intelligence (AI) on language teaching and how it can change traditional language learning methodologies. Moreover, it discusses artificial intelligence (AI) powered language learning sites as ELSA Speak, Mondly, Babbel and Cake, which provides personalized content recommendations, adaptive learning paths and real-time pronunciation analysis. These platforms provide personalized and engaging educational experiences that can let students get immediate feedback and concentrate on their weak areas. Furthermore, by changing the roles of educators and encouraging active engagement AI's integration into language instruction creates inclusive learning environment. The article highlights the potential of AI in enhancing language proficiency and making learning language more accessible to every learner.

Keywords: AI in language learning, pronunciation feedback, Duolingo, ELSA Speak and adaptive learning

Introduction

The increasing evolution and integration of artificial intelligence (AI) is causing a fundamental revolution in English language acquisition. The article examines how AI-powered platforms are developing language learning by going beyond traditional methods to provide engaging, individual and adaptive experiences. It explores the essential features of AI-powered chatbots, adaptive vocabulary, grammar exercises and speech recognition. It demonstrates the usefulness and advantages of AI in language learning by looking at well-known systems like ELSA Speak, Mondly, Babble and Cake. The article aims to present through analysis the revolutionary potential of AI in language learning supported by significant research and real-world experiences.

The Transformative Power of AI in Language Learning:

The rise of AI-powered platforms significantly influences learning English. The way language learners use the language is being improved by these resources which offer individualized and flexible experiences that were unavailable some years ago. This revolution is centered on AI's capacity to create personalized learning methods. This platform can evaluate and identify each student's strengths and limitations and also modify the curriculum and degree of difficulty of the lesson. It ensures that each student focuses on their areas of greatest need for improvement. Studies on adaptive learning systems state that this approach enhances engagement and effectiveness with proving research that adaptive systems significantly improve learning results (Brusilovsky & Peylo, 2003). The Holmes, Bialik, and Fadel (2019) stated that increasing integration of AI in education shows the growing reliance on AI to achieve truly personalized learning experiences. Artificial automatic speech recognition and pronunciation feedback are key aspects of these technologies. By studying the learner's pronunciation, AI gives immediate and comprehensive feedback on fluency and accuracy. Identifying specific pronunciation problems helps students focus on areas that need work. Chatbots are helpful platforms for learning a language, especially when fostering conversational skills. (Fryer et al., 2019). Students can learn vital information about their development through performance analysis and progress tracking. AI-powered platforms track students' progress and offer data on their performance and areas for improvement. These insights enable students to monitor their progress and adjust their learning style. Sience and Gasevic (2012) claimed that learning analytics can provide valuable insight into learners' performance and behavior, enabling target recommendations and activities. The growth of data-driven education further emphasises the importance of these analytics in optimising learning outcomes

Popular AI-powered Language Learning Platforms and Tools

1. ELSA Speak

ELSA Speak: An AI-powered speech recognition technology that provides immediate and comprehensive feedback on pronunciation. It identifies particular sounds that need work and provides personal lessons based on the user's original tongue and pronunciation patterns. Students use this app to get confidence in their speaking and get immediate and useful feedback.

Moreover, teachers can use this app to enhance pronunciation instruction in the classroom, especially for students who struggle with specific sounds. Additionally, they can give tasks for homework and analyze each student's progress in pronunciation. Witt and Young's (2000) study on automated speech recognition in language acquisition provides evidence for the effectiveness of these technologies in enhancing pronunciation accuracy.

2. Mondly

Mondly AI-powered chatbot and speech recognition which provides conversational language learning experience that emphasizes practical language through real-life scenarios and dialogues. Effective communication is made possible by the app's many languages and learning routes. Chatbots allow students to participate in interactive discussions, practice speaking through voice recognition exercises, study grammar and vocabulary in context and improve their listening skills through audio. Teachers use Mondly to enhance vocabulary and grammar by providing conversational practice. Conversational AI is a useful tool for language practice and improvement, according to research on chat-assisted language learning.

3. Babel

Babel is a tool that creates language training with an emphasis on real-world communication using artificial intelligence. Students can improve their pronunciation because of the app's speech recognition. Students use the app to improve their pronunciation and get immediate feedback and learn conversational skills. Additionally, teachers can develop students' vocabulary and conversational skills and assign courses to students to enhance classroom learning. Many researchers demonstrated the efficacy of spaced repetition techniques in improving long-term vocabulary recall.

4. Cake

Cake uses short videos from YouTube, TV series, and movies to teach English. The usage of this (AI) artificial intelligence helps with spoken comprehension and pronunciation. The tool offers transcripts and subtitles. Students can improve their pronunciation and listening comprehension through entertaining video clips and can learn common phrases. Teachers can use this app to enhance their lessons in the classroom by introducing common English words, improving pronunciation, listening and playing video games. Studies have demonstrated that using real videos to teach languages is a successful teaching strategy.

The Benefits of AI-Powered Language Learning Platforms.

AI-powered language learning platforms have emerged, ushering in a new era of Accessibility and productivity in language learning. These platforms provide several benefits that traditional methods often struggle to match. AI language learning technologies automate tasks and offer individualized learning experiences depending on learner's needs and success (Xie, Chu, Hwang & Wang, 2019). They offer rapid feedback and improvements to help students improve their skills faster. AI language learning technologies offer personalized learning experiences by tracking user progress and personalizing content to their unique needs and abilities. Kessler (2018) suggests that adapting material to learners' learning style and speed can enhance engagement and efficiency in the learning process. Another significant

advantage is the availability of 24/7 learning, which helps students to integrate language acquisition into active lives by accessing classes and practicing it anytime and anywhere. As demonstrated by the effectiveness of adaptive testing (Wainer et al., 2000) and the well-established principles of spaced repetitions in memory retention (Ebbinghaus, 1885), learners retain information more effectively when this constant accessibility is paired with adoptive exercises and spaced repetition. Finally, data-driven progress tracking supports the wider advantages of learning analytics in personalized education by allowing students to access their progress, pinpoint areas for growth and maintain motivation (Siemens & Gasevic, 2012).

Conclusion

Language learning platforms driven by AI are an important achievement in educational technology. These platforms are modifying the way people learn and become proficient in new languages by offering personalized learning experiences, immediate feedback, and engaging and interactive features. The advantages, which are backed by studies and real-world applications, demonstrate how AI has the potential to democratize education and improve the effectiveness and accessibility of language acquisition. Creating more complex and engaging language learning experiences as AI technology develops will improve people's capacity to interact and communicate across linguistic and cultural divides. The development of AI will significantly impact language learning in the future, offering students everywhere more individualized, effective and interesting educational experiences.

References

1. De la Vall, R. R. F., & Araya, F. G. (2023). Exploring the benefits and challenges of AI-language learning tools. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Invention*, 10(01), 7569-7576.
2. Kuddus, K. (2022). Artificial intelligence in language learning: Practices and prospects. *Advanced analytics and deep learning models*, 1-17.
3. Lakshmi, N. (2024). AI: A Tech Platform for Revolutionized English Language Teaching & Learning. *Techtalk: Revolutionising English Language Teaching in the 21st Century*, 85.
4. Mitra, N., & Banerjee, A. (2022). A study on using AI in promoting English language learning. In *Emerging Technologies in Data Mining and Information Security: Proceedings of IEMIS 2022, Volume 2* (pp. 287-297). Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore.
5. Negrila, A. M. C. (2023). The new revolution in language learning: The power of artificial intelligence and education 4.0. *Bulletin of "Carol I" National Defence University (EN)*, 12(02), 16-27.

6. Opyr, M., Dobrovolska, S., & Panchyshyn, S. (2022). Artificial intelligence for learning English.

Vijayakumar, M., & Chellapandiyan, G. (2024). Language Learning Through AI Technology-LLA (Language Learning Apps). *International Research Journal on Advanced Engineering and Management (IRJAEM)*, 2(04), 957-962